

CONTENT LINES FROM THE SUBJECT OF THE AZERBAIJANI LANGUAGE

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Abstract

Integration is both a strategy and an end result of education. In this process, in addition to mastering the integrative content and methodology, the student's age, understanding level, and psychological characteristics should not be overlooked.

It is difficult to find reference points and to explain the knowledge to be mastered at intersection points without understanding the relationship between the contents of the Azerbaijani language.

If the student understands that speech sounds create words, phrases and sentences, and if he understands this factor as a language regularity, then he will have a broad and comprehensive idea about speech and the world of speech.

The process of integration in education is a rather complex, multifaceted concept due to the number of indicators. The main goal of training based on integration is to create a holistic impression of the world and knowledge, and to ensure the general mental development of students.

Keywords: Speech sounds, integration, active learning, curriculum, content communication, language regularity.

Integration, which is one of the main components of a modern lesson, manifests itself in two ways:

1. Interdisciplinary integration;
2. Internal integration.

The system of integration relations, which reflects the cause-and-effect, time, quantitative relations between the subjects of the subject, the sections of the course, and the knowledge within the scope of the studied object is widely used, is called intra-subject integration. That is, intra-subject integration is the connection of a new topic with previous topics within the same subject.

This integration can be both in the same class during one school year, and in different classes in previous years. Cross-curricular integration allows students to review their previous knowledge of a subject and connect it with newly learned knowledge, and at the same time, develop creative thinking in relation to the topics to be studied in the future.

From this point of view, in the teaching of the subject of the Azerbaijani language in high school, integrativeness is always in the center of attention as one of the main components of the lesson. Starting from primary classes, it is impossible to imagine Azerbaijani language classes without internal integration.

Since the language itself is a structural-semantic unit, it is mastered by analogous inductive and deductive methods. Knowing the intra-subject relationship is very important for the theoretical preparation of the teachers teaching the Azerbaijani language and for applying language facts in practice. [2, 22]

The current map of intra-subject communication in the teaching of the Azerbaijani language shows that it is impossible not to take advantage of it on the way from sound to the interpretation of large texts. For this, the following should be expected in mastering language rules:

1. Intra-subject communication should be taken into account in the curricula, it should be given a wide place in the explanatory sheets and methodical materials;

2. To use intra-disciplinary communication, topics, inter-section transitions should be defined correctly;

3. Methods, means, methods and technologies related to intra-disciplinary communication should be summarized.

An intra-curricular connection is established between the pre-alphabet period, the alphabet learning period and the post-alphabet learning stages in primary grades. The mother tongue curriculum includes the following educational components related to the teaching of this subject:

1. General training results;
2. Main content lines;
3. Learning outcomes for each content line for different levels of education (primary, basic, secondary);
4. Content standards for classes;
5. Interdisciplinary and intra-disciplinary integration;
6. Training technologies: forms and methods;
7. Valuation matters. [2, 118-119]

As you can see, interdisciplinary and intra-disciplinary integration has a leading position as a training component. It can only affect the quality of teaching if the teacher, starting from the primary grade, can build integration by having a clear idea of the end goal of the overall learning according to the content line for each grade.

The content lines in mother tongue education are defined as follows:

- listening, understanding and speaking;
- read
- writing
- language rules.

Here, the first three lines directly form speech skills, and language rules are a means to acquire speech skills. Linguistic rules in text work help to develop speech habits. According to the curriculum, language rules should not be memorized in isolation from real speech, but should be learned to be applied in appropriate situations in oral and written speech.

According to the content line of language rules, students master a number of linguistic concepts (syllables, letters, sounds, vowels, consonants, alphabetical order, sentences) from the 1st grade, and these concepts are further deepened at the next stage. Of course, in the first grades, they get an idea of the essence by using less linguistic terms. For the stage of secondary general education, the Azerbaijani language course is defined by classes as follows:

- Class V - phonetics, lexicology, word creation
- VI-VII classes – morphology
- Grades VIII-IX – syntax
- Class X - speech culture
- Class XI - stylistics.

As it can be seen, in terms of connecting the language facts learned in different classes, intra-disciplinary integration is of great importance. [4, 122]

In Azerbaijani language classes, intra-subject integration can be implemented at different levels and forms. One of these tools is linguistic analysis. Linguistic analysis, which includes all types of analysis, can be used in the process of learning a new topic related to previous topics, in checking general knowledge on topics, as well as in work classes on studies.

The essence of this analysis is the examination of different language facts on the same sample. Thus, the linguistic analysis not only ensures the examination of the word, which is the main unit of the language, in different categories, but also clearly reveals the relationship between these categories.

When concluding individual sections, it is necessary to determine the analysis in such a way that the students can procedurally use all the knowledge they have learned up to grade IV, and at the same time prepare a certain ground about the essence of the language rules to be learned in grades V-IX.

A picture of an orchard with various trees is hung from the board (or displayed on the screen). Then the class is addressed:

- 1) What is depicted in the picture (screen)?
- 2) What do you see in the garden?
- 3) What kind of fruits are they?
- 4) How to name the area where individual fruit trees are located?

The answers "garden", "fruit garden", "yellow, red", "colorful" are received from the students. Then the students are asked to make a sentence from those words and the received sentence is written on the board. [2, 44]

What fruit trees are there in the garden?

After that, students are involved in research to answer the following questions:

- What categories does the same word have at different levels of the language?

As a form of work, depending on the number of students in the class, the form of work with small groups or pairs is used. Each group or pair is given a specific task related to the sentence on the board:

- Group I - to analyze the sentence syntactically
- Group II – to phonetically analyze the words in the sentence
- Group III – lexical analysis of words
- Group IV – morphological analysis of words.

Groups perform the task and are asked to visualize their work on the table. Students work according to a schedule prepared in advance on large paper. Using the round-robin method, groups (or pairs) complete the table, each working in the columns corresponding to their task.

Then the chart is hung on the board and the students are involved in the discussion. During the discussion, the comparison of the categories is focused and the research question is answered as a result.

In order to develop students' creative thinking, their attention is drawn to the same category belonging to different levels, and students come to the conclusion through comparison that the same word has different categories in different language layers, and the same category appears differently in different levels. For example, the word colorful is a morphologically complex word according to its structure, but it is a syntactically simple member. [6, 39]

Thus, students clearly understand that the concepts of simplicity and complexity have different characteristics at different levels.

After that, you can work on the sentence in terms of connection with future lessons. The students' attention is drawn to the reconciliation of the message with the prophet and the reason for the violation of the reconciliation is clarified. The students are asked to answer that the text does not agree with it in terms of quantity because it mentions an inanimate object in the text, and they are told that this is a grammatical norm. If the news was quantitatively consistent, for example, "flowers have opened", then the norm would be violated. The norm is speech culture, and it will be discussed later.

Thus, it is clear that linguistic analysis is of great importance in connecting the past lesson with the future lesson, and it can be effective for teachers to use it properly.

In the Concept of General Education (National Curriculum) of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the goals and tasks of secondary education, including each of its levels, and the expected learning outcomes are explained in detail.

The main essence of the curriculum application is that the educated citizen acquires life skills. In order to have a high level of life skills, the student must have basic knowledge of all subjects and be able to apply what he has learned. [5, 2]

Rapid social, cultural and technological changes in the modern world greatly increase the importance of a global mindset. Such a solution leads to treating students in the learning process not as passive consumers of knowledge and skills given in separate subjects, but on the contrary, as subjects who have a creative attitude towards understanding the world around them. This is possible when the subjects studied at the educational levels and the topics covered by them are taught not separately, but in a connected-integrative way.

The current world experience shows that it is impossible to achieve the desired results in the teaching of any subject, including the Azerbaijani language, without using various integrations in the learning process.

Thus, the role of integration in the stimulation of training, the provision of students' activity, the detailed

mastering of the content and the formation of the students' scientific outlook is undeniable. Integration improves the learning process, serves to deepen the interaction and dependence between disciplines.

With the help of integration, students understand the interrelationships between knowledge and use that knowledge to solve personal and social problems. The issue of what level of integration is a topic of discussion among many scientists.

Among the subjects in which the Azerbaijani language is integrated in the primary classes are a foreign language, mathematics, informatics, "Life science", technology, music, physics, physical education, visual arts, etc. subjects can be included.

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